
Prominence in the Newspaper Coverage of Conspiracy Theories during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Nigeria

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Abstract

The researchers examined newspaper coverage of conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria. The study was aimed at assessing one critical issue on the conspiracy theories during the COVID-19-pandemic in Nigeria which is the prominence in the print newspapers coverage in Nigeria. The gate-keeping theory was employed in this regard. The researchers adopted the content analysis with the coding sheet as instrument for data collection. A sample size of two newspapers, the *Nation* and *Punch* published from April 2020 to March 2021 (Monday-Friday) were derived from a population size of five hundred and twenty-two newspapers using purposive sampling technique. Findings showed that the *Punch* and *Nation* newspapers gave adequate coverage to the COVID-19 pandemic with 2,318 stories or 94.7%, 124 of them on conspiracy theories representing 5.5%. Based on the findings, it was concluded that the select newspapers reported the COVID-19 pandemic, though not so for the conspiracy theories and no prominence was attached to the stories as more than three-quarter of the stories (97) or 81.5% were tucked inside the pages of the newspapers analysed and 4 or 3.2% on the front page. Furthermore, 31 representing 33.7% were 21 paragraphs and above in the *Nation* while the *Punch* newspaper had 6 stories representing 18.8% with the same number of paragraphs. There is significant relationship between the story types of the conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic and the prominence attached to the newspapers coverage as the minimum expected count of .26 is less than 5. Thus, the researchers recommended that the print media houses in Nigeria should endeavour to focus on stories that will educate Nigerians the more on issues of conspiracy theories by making the stories prominent by bringing them on the front burner of the newspapers.

Keywords: Conspiracy Theory, Newspaper Coverage, Gatekeeping theory and COVID-19 Pandemic

Introduction

Throughout history, pandemics have had significant health implications and have presented a grave threat to the survival of the human race. The rapid spread of infections, such as COVID-19, can impose a significant strain on the healthcare system, leading to limited access to healthcare services and increased mortality rates for both communicable and non-communicable illnesses.

Nigeria, one of the countries affected by COVID-19 was not spared the various controversies surrounding the pandemic and reported by some newspapers and social

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media platforms. Statistics revealed that large portions of ordinary citizens endorse newspaper coverage over a wide range of topics (Oliver & Wood, Sunstein & Vermeule cited in Jan-Willem & Karen, 2017). Apart from being on the internet, the controversies became topics of discussion within homes and among individuals and groups. The word, “conspiracy” was first coined by Suetonius or Machiavelli (cited in Giry & Tika, 2020) in his review paper on “conspiracy theories in political science and political theory” where they described it as a phenomenon and a subject of analysis both by political scientists and philosophers. However, Popper (cited in Coady, 2023, p.1), argued that true conspiracies actually exist as only few things successfully happen as predicted. Douglas *et al* (cited in Olusoji *et al* 2020, p.153) define conspiracy theories as “attempts to explain the ultimate causes of significant social and political events and circumstances with claims of secret plots by two or more powerful actors.” It is the belief that some powerful organisations or conspirators are responsible for an occurrence that cannot be explained or substantiated (Olatunji *et al* 2020, p.153). This means that powerful actors are engaged in wide range of secret activities for their own personal gain. In other words, conspiracy theories are phenomena buried in myths: unfortunately, most people prefer to believe myths over scientific evidence (Constantinou, Kagialis & Karekla, 2021). Thus, without an iota of scientific proof, the average human person rationalises conspiracy theories in his/her imaginative view and shares or disseminates such information with others. This trend is quite common on the internet and other social media platforms.

There are also claims that conspiracy theories were borne out of the need to cope with fearful situation and douse tension. In a bid to rationalise events that are inexplicable to reduce tension, most humans tend to believe in imagined (vs factual) theories (Franks, Bangerter & Bauer cited in Constantinou, Kagialis & Karekla, 2021). Unlike in ancient Greeks, today myths and conspiracy theories are formed with some blend of truth and fabricated components (Taher, Mannan, Dulal, Gida cited in Constantinou, Kagialis & Karekla, 2021).

In light of the significant influx of information following the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, the World Health Organisation (WHO) officially recognised and labelled the phenomenon as an "infodemic" in March 2020. The WHO defines an infodemic as a situation wherein an excessive amount of information, including false or misleading content, is disseminated across digital and physical platforms during a disease outbreak (Eysenbach, 2020; WHO, 2022). In June 2020, the World Health Organisation (2020) went further in its first WHO *Infodemiology Conference*, following a preparatory online crowd-sourcing process to develop a policy framework to fight infodemics (Eysenbach, 2020). This study examined the prominence attached to newspaper coverage of conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The traditional media such as the newspapers, television or local and international, have played and continue to play important roles in informing the citizens about the facts concerning the COVID-19 pandemic virus and stating the right and truthful information (De Coninck, 2021). Thus, the media have the power to direct our attention towards health issues, by setting agenda through communication, vital in the struggle to create awareness in eradicating the coronavirus (Maryam, cited in Kent, 2020, p.3). In other words, traditional media, especially newspapers, other than social media, are generally

more widely used and seen as a credible source of information (OECD, cited in Wolf, 2022).

The mass media via newspapers disseminate information concerning health in the published newspapers. This, therefore, necessitated the need for more investigation to be carried out in the area of the prominence attached to the stories. In noting this fact, Kente (2020, p.3) observed that with the growing concern about the spread of the COVID-19 virus variant and the need for more awareness and educative campaigns in Nigeria, the role of the mass media especially the newspapers to give a more in-depth and detailed account of information about COVID-19 should be assessed to serve as a basis for the increase in public knowledge on the COVID-19 conspiracy theories. Onyebuchi in Guanah (2018) says the media, through its process of news selection, establishes not only issues of public importance but also determines how much importance to attach to such issues. In line with this perspective, this is an assessment of the prominence in the print newspaper coverage of conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research question was designed to guide the study:

1. What is the prominence attached to conspiracy theories in the print newspaper coverage of conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis: Ho: There is no significant relationship between the story types and conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic covered by the print newspapers in Nigeria.

Conceptualising Conspiracy Theories

In modern societies, conspiracy theories have become a widespread phenomenon defined as a belief that a group of people secretly works to achieve some malevolent goal (Banai, Banai & Miklousic, 2021). Douglas *et al* (2019) see conspiracy theory as “attempts to explain the ultimate causes of significant social and political events, circumstances with the claims of secret plots by two or more powerful actors (Brotherton *et al* 2013; Imhoff & Bruder, 2013; Lewandowsky *et al* 2013b; Uscinski *et al* 2016) in (Klofstad *et al*, 2019). The idea behind the secret plots, according to Radnitz & Underwood (cited in Ndinojuo, 2020, *ibid*) “is to usurp political or economic power, violate rights, infringe upon established agreements, withhold vital secrets and to alter bedrock institutions.”

Furthermore, Gambo & Shem (2021) view conspiracy theory as “an effort to explain some events or practice by reference to the machinations of powerful people, who have also managed to conceal their role.” “Conspiracy theories” refer to any effort to explain the rationale behind the occurrence of social or political circumstances, with claims of secret plots by either two or more powerful actors (Gambo & Shem, 2021).

Conspiracy Theories and Health Pandemics

Past health crises provided some insights into the development of conspiracy theories concerning viruses. There has been an element of mistrust toward the mainstream media, influential authorities and or government institutions which seemed to have facilitated the endorsement and spread of conspiracy theories throughout past epidemics such as Zika (2017; Smallman, 2015), Ebola or HINI (Leonard & Phillipe, 2021).

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The Zika virus is spread primarily through the bite of an infected mosquito, but it can be sexually transmitted (Campos *et al* 2015). According to Klofstad *et al* (2019), infection during pregnancy could cause birth defects, including microcephaly (Nunes *et al* 2016 cited in Klofstad *et al* 2019). However, rather than relying on authoritative sources of information, such as the World Health Organisation, which states that Zika is a naturally occurring virus, many people trafficked in conspiracy theories to explain Zika.

Conspiracy beliefs about the Origin of HIV and the role of government in the AIDS epidemic are prevalent, particularly in the African American community (Ross, Essien & Torres, 2006). A random door-to-door survey of African Americans in California that 27% of African Americans endorsed the belief that “HIV/AIDS is a man-made virus that federal government made to kill and wipe out black people” and a further 23% were unsure.

The outbreak of COVID-19 is not without its controversies and conspiracy theories. For instance, the Chinese government in late 2019, placed Wuhan on lockdown and cancelled the celebrations of the Chinese New Year and it was reported in *The Washington Times* that the novel coronavirus is a biological weapon developed at the Wuhan Institute of Virology (Gertz, 2020). Thus, beginning from the virus outbreak, conspiracy theories about its ethology continued to trail it as some scientists and media outlets initially referred to the virus as the Wuhan Virus. President Donald Trump of the United States equally blamed the Chinese for what he termed the “kung flu” and accused the WHO, media, and Democrats of promoting media hysteria, by exaggerating the death rate and impact of the outbreak, as a ploy to bring him down”(BBC News, 2020).

Newspapers Coverage of Health Pandemics

According to Ndaliman & Monday (2013, p.159), communication scholars assert that the print media remains highly significant and continues to exert a profound influence on our daily lives. They argue that newspapers, in particular, not only retain their relevance, but also play a crucial role in shaping public opinion on various societal matters. Bittner (2005) and Ndaliman & Monday (2013, p. 159) have presented arguments highlighting the significance of print media as a crucial component of mass communication. They posit that print media maintains a prominent position in modern societies by delivering well-researched content that stimulates individuals to engage in creative thinking and elicit positive responses.

In Dominick’s (2009) view, newspapers are widely favoured in modern societies due to a multitude of factors. Ndaliman & Monday (2013, p.159), identify one of them as newspapers ability to prioritise the coverage of significant issues, which is evident through their strategic placement, attention-grabbing headlines and extensive coverage. Additionally, Ndaliman & Monday (2013) have substantiated the significance of print media in fostering the advancement and maturation of any given society, emphasising that the absence of a newspaper impedes progress. According to McQuail (2005, p.162), newspapers are believed to have both objective effects on society and a social purpose. In terms of the objective effect, newspapers are supposed to fulfill certain objectives as the ‘Fourth Estate of the Realm’ and at the same time serve as a means of entertainment and relaxation for certain people.

Empirical Review

Empirical studies relating to health pandemics and conspiracy theories have been carried out by researchers. Clarke (2002) argues that academics usually take a “dismissive attitude” towards conspiracy theories, yet, as he puts it, these beliefs- along with broader narratives that undermine trust can have key implications during an epidemic. Numerous studies have been conducted in diverse domains such as health pandemics, conspiracy theories, COVID-19, and infodemiology.

Van Prooijen & Douglas (2017) conducted a study that explored the relationship between conspiracy theories and historical events, specifically focusing on the role of societal crises. The research examined the correlation between societal crises and individuals' inclination towards endorsing conspiracy theories. The study conducted by Olatunji, Ayandele, Ashirudeen & Olaniru (2020) examined the phenomenon of "infodemic" within the context of a pandemic, specifically focusing on the proliferation of COVID-19 conspiracy theories within an African country. The present study aimed to investigate prevalent conspiracy theories surrounding COVID-19 in Nigeria, while also shedding light on the primary sources of COVID-19 information among Nigerians and their perceived level of trustworthiness. According to the study, there is a perception in Nigeria that the government and media have exaggerated the COVID-19 infection situation and some individuals view it as a potential Chinese biological weapon. It has been observed that traditional media is widely regarded as the primary source of information, whereas information from political leaders and social media is often viewed as lacking credibility.

Ogbonna (2020) examined conspiracy theories and misinformation in the coverage of the COVID-19 pandemic: An assessment of online newspapers in Nigeria. The researcher examined conspiracy theories on the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. Findings showed that the various conspiracy theories and misinformation were adequately given coverage, while counterarguments in refuting the theories and misinformation exist.

Theoretical Framework

The Gate-Keeping Theory

The concept of gate-keeping theory was originally introduced by Kurt Lewin, an Australian scholar, in the year 1947. Content curation is the systematic procedure of selecting and refining messages or information for distribution, whether through publishing, broadcasting, the internet, or any other communication medium. The theory is grounded in the notion that no media organisation is capable of disseminating every single message it receives during its daily operations (Esimokha, 2014, p.112). The concept of gatekeeping in the news industry was first recognised in the literature as far back as 1922; although, it was not formally labelled as such at that time (Shoemaker & Vos, 2009). Gatekeeping theory examines the process of selecting and moulding news messages that are disseminated within society (Shoemaker & Vos, 2009) as discussed in the work of Welbers & Ogenhaffen (2018).

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According to McQuail (2005, cited in Ibraheem & Garba, 2019), the concept of "gatekeeping" is used metaphorically to explain the decision-making process involved in media work. Specifically, it refers to the evaluation of whether a specific news report should be permitted to pass through the metaphorical "gates" of a news medium and be broadcast on a news channel. He further stated that the concept of gatekeeping has a broader scope, as it can be extended to the roles of literary agents and publishers, as well as various forms of editorial and production work in print and television. This primarily pertains to the decision-making processes surrounding the distribution and marketing of pre-existing media products.

Method

The researchers investigated print newspapers coverage of conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic. The content analysis research design was found appropriate because it provided a comprehensive understanding of the research variables. Content analysis is the research design adopted by this study. This research design is appropriate when the aim is to examine the manifest content of communication in the *Punch* and *Nation* newspapers. It is a research design that is focused on measuring the manifest content of communication. Content analysis, according to Kente (2020, p.12), is an appropriate method because it allows a closeness to text which can alternate between specific categories and relationships and also statistically analyses the coded form of text, as well as provides insight into complex models of human thought and language use. The population of this study covered issues published from April 2020 to March 2021 (Monday-Friday), a total of 522 editions of the newspapers were content analysed. The justification for this sample size and period covered the height of the COVID-19 pandemic and reports on the issue were rife then.

Thus, conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic were a top agenda as newspapers participated in contributing their voices to debates and controversies on issues, which topped the agenda of the issues. The number of editions per month from the period mapped for the study are as follows: 1) April 2020 (22 editions); 2) May 2020 (21); 3) June 2020 (22), 4) July 2020 (23); 5) August 2020 (21); 6) September 2020 (22); 7) October 2020 (22); 8) November 2020 (21); 9) December 2020 (23); 10) January 2021 (21); 11) February 2021 (20); and 12) March 2021 (23 editions). Total= 261*2 newspapers- (522 editions). Apart from the above rationale for the choice of newspapers, other factors include: They are national in outlook, they are published daily, they are inclusive of weekend publications, they have a wide readership throughout Nigeria, they newspapers have a corporate reputation and their ownership is mainly private pattern (Okoro, Ukonu, Eze & Odoemelam, 2014).

Data Presentation and Analysis

The data obtained from the *Punch* and *Nation* newspapers (print) on the frequency of conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria is presented in the Fig below:

Line Chart:1: Shows the frequency in the print and online newspapers coverage of conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria. The information in the figure above reveals that the print newspapers reported the COVID-19 pandemic stories not related to the conspiracy theories with a total of 2,194, representing 94.7%, while 124 stories representing 5.3% were not related to the conspiracy theories. A breakdown of this figure shows that *The Nation* newspaper had more coverage of the non-conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic with 1,136 cases, representing 92.5%, while stories relating to the conspiracy theories were 92, which represents 7.5% of the entire stories on COVID-19 pandemic coverage by the newspapers. On the other hand, the *Punch* newspaper reported 1,058 cases which represents 97.1% on the non-conspiracy theory-related stories, but less in the coverage of conspiracy theories with 32 cases representing 2.9%. The bar chart below shows the story's position on conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic in the print newspapers coverage in Nigeria.

Table 1: Shows the prominence (story positioning) in the print newspapers coverage of conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria based on story placement

	Story Prominence/Position			
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cummulative Percent
Valid Front Page	4	3.2	3.2	3.2
Inside Page	97	78.2	78.2	81.5
Back Page	23	18.5	18.5	100.0
Total	124	100.0	100.0	

Source: Content Analysis Data

The findings show that stories on conspiracy theories during the COVID pandemic were not given prominence as shown by newspaper reports. For example, more than three-quarters of the stories, (97) or 81.5% were tucked inside the pages of the newspapers

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analysed, followed by the back page (23) or 18.5%, while the front page which is supposed to be a prominent position for any story published in the print newspapers observed only meagre (4) or 3.2%.

Table 2: Shows the prominence attached to the conspiracy theories in the print newspapers coverage of conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria.

	Story Depth			
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cummulative Percent
Valid 1-5 Paragraphs	9	6.5	6.5	6.5
6-10 Paragraphs	29	20.9	20.9	27.4
11-15 Paragraphs	34	24.4	24.4	51.8
16-20 Paragraphs	30	21.6	21.6	73.4
21 & Above	37	26.6	26.6	100.0
Total	139	100.0	100.0	

Source: Content Analysis Data

As a follow-up to the prominence attached to the stories on conspiracy theories by the print newspaper, the table above showed that more than a quarter of the stories, 31 representing 33.7% were 21 paragraphs and above in the *Nation*, the *Punch* newspaper had 6 stories representing 18.8% with the same number of paragraphs. Conversely, most of the stories, 12 representing 37.5% by the *Punch* newspaper have 11-15 paragraphs as juxtaposed to 17 stories representing 18.5% with 11-15 paragraphs printed in the *Nation* newspaper.

Similar stories with 16-20 paragraphs by the *Nation* newspaper have 24, representing 26.1% as compared to 5 stories representing 15.6% in the *Punch* newspaper. The majority of the story paragraphs run through close to a quarter, except the 21 and above paragraphs which is more than 29.8%, while 1-5 paragraph stories fall to 5 or just 4% in all.

Null Hypothesis (Ho): There is no significant relationship between the prominence attached to the story and conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic by the print newspapers coverage in Nigeria.

Table 3: Shows the relationship between the prominence attached to the stories of the conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria

		Story Prominence/Position * Type of Conspiracy Theory Cross-tabulation					Total	
		Type of Conspiracy Theory						
		Man- God- MadeSent Virus Virus	Alternative Disease Models	Hoax - Govt. Distrust	The Vaccine - Tool for Pandemic Foreign Domination and Profiteering	Safety, Efficac y and Quality Concer ns		
Story Prominence/Position	Front Page	3	0	0	0	0	1	4

	within Type of Conspiracy Theory	Count	29	9	9	30	7	13	97
	%	%	74.4%	90.0%	81.8%	76.9%	87.5%	76.5%	78.2%
	Back Page	Count	7	1	2	9	1	3	23
	%	%	17.9%	10.0%	18.2%	23.1%	12.5%	17.6%	18.5%
Total	within Type of Conspiracy Theory	Count	39	10	11	39	8	17	124
	%	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	%	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Decision Rule

The Chi-Square tests show that the null hypothesis is overruled as the minimum expected count of .26 is less than 5. The Chi-Square tests below show that the null hypothesis is overruled. This, therefore, implies that there is significant relationship between the types of the conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic and the prominence attached to the newspapers coverage.

Table 4: Shows the Test of Chi-Square on the relationship between the prominence attached to the stories in the print newspapers coverage of conspiracy theories during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.349 ^a	10	0.785
Likelihood Ratio	7.847	10	0.644
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.362	1	0.547
N of Valid Cases	124		

a. 10 cells (55.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .26

Symmetric Measures

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		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	0.226	0.785
	Cramer's V	0.160	0.785
N of Valid Cases		124	

The main research objective is to evaluate the prominence attached to the stories in the print newspaper coverage of conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria. It is evident from the data gathered that Nigerian newspapers did not give much prominence to conspiracy theories in their publications during the heat of the COVID-19 pandemic as shown in the table above. Even though over 2,318 stories on the COVID-19 pandemic were reported by the two print newspapers.

Table 4 shows the relationship between the prominence attached to the story and the conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic in the print newspaper coverage in Nigeria. A breakdown of this relationship between the prominence attached to the story and conspiracy theories shows that the inside pages reported most of the Pandemic hoax-with distrust of the Government (30), Man-made virus (29), God-sent virus and COVID-19 as an Alternative disease model (9) each respectively, while the Vaccine-Tool for foreign domination and profiteering with (1) each on the inside page respectively.

The back page follows with stories on the coverage of COVID-19 conspiracy theories with Pandemic hoax distrust of the Government (9), the virus as Man-made (7), Safety, efficacy and quality concerns of the vaccines (3), while God-sent and the vaccine as tool for foreign domination and profiteering with (1) each respectively reported on the back page of the newspapers. However, the front page which indicates the prominence attached to the conspiracy theories observed a few appearances, of Man-made viruses (3), while the story on the Safety, efficacy and quality concerns occurred (1) on the front page of the newspapers under investigation.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the above analysis, there is a relationship between the prominence attached to the conspiracy theories on the COVID-19 pandemic and the print newspaper coverage in Nigeria. This does not mean that the two newspapers gave prominence to conspiracy theories in their coverage. Editors or gatekeepers decide where to place news stories that are disseminated within the society in their medium (Shoemaker & Reese, 1996; Shoemaker & Vos, 2009). Various media ascribe importance to issues through the prominence given to the report (Okoro & Agbo; cited in Ate (2008). In view of this, the present study is supported by a similar one done by the Urban Action Group (2015) (UAG) which revealed that only 11 per cent of the newspaper's reportage on the Ebola Virus Disease was on the front and back pages.

Literature also found support with Schultziner & Stukalin (2021) who argued that businesses as well as political considerations shape the decision of newspapers on what to report and how to report it. In other words, newspaper editors may decide not to give prominence to certain issues as is applicable in the coverage of conspiracy theories on the pandemic. This could then mean that Nigerian newspapers overlooked the issue of

conspiracy theories even while paying greater attention to the coverage of COVID-19. The inference could be drawn that newspaper editors in Nigeria may have avoided issues of conspiracy theories which they deemed to be controversial. Literature reveals that the press sets agenda on issues that are of importance to the general public based on the coverage of conspiracy theories in Nigeria. The literature also reiterates the view suggesting that the media coverage may be simply a reflection of public concerns that already exist (Goa (cited in Guanah, 2018, p.112),

Conclusion

In assessing the prominence in the reportage of conspiracy theories, the findings showed that for the over 2,318 stories on the COVID-19 pandemic by the print newspapers, only 124 of them are on conspiracy theories and of this number, only 4 or 3.2% appeared on the front page of the *Nation* newspaper, while none appeared on the front page of the *Punch* newspaper. However, more than three-quarters, that is, 97 of the stories on conspiracy theories representing 78.2% were reported on the inside page of the newspapers. Apart from not giving adequate coverage to conspiracy theories, Nigerian newspapers did not also give attention or prominence to the issues of conspiracy theories, just as 4 or 3.2% of stories on the conspiracy theory appeared on the front pages of the *Nation* newspaper.

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